

Genetic studies on purple pigmentation in rice and its use in breeding two-line rice hybrids

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Many scientists, particularly those in Japan, have systematically studied how purple color is inherited in rice leaves. Three pairs of basic genes (*C*, *A*, *P*) control the inheritance of anthocyanin pigments (Nagao 1951 and Takashi 1957). The *C-A-P* gene system in japonica rice is suitable for indica rice (Kinoshita 1984). All *C*, *A*, *P* genes have their multiple alleles as well as several main genes with multiple effects. The gene *Pl*, for example, is responsible for giving leaves, nodes, internodes, sheath, and leaf rings their purple color. At least one or two pairs of inhibitor genes influence the expression of purple leaf color.

We studied the inheritance of two newly discovered purple rice lines and the possibility of their use as gene markers in hybrid rice breeding.

OPL and PL 184 with purple leaves were discovered in fields planted to normal green varieties Ketan Nangka and W6184S in 1988 and 1990, respectively. (They were crossed with each other and then crossed with IRRI variety IR1552 in 1991 and 1992.) The resulting F_1 s and F_2 s were purple, and no segregation in F_2 populations was found, inferring that OPL, PL 184, and IR1552 may have allelic genes controlling purple pigmentation of seedlings. However, when OPL and PL 184 were crossed with 23 normal green rice cultivars or lines (12 indica thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines, 2 japonica photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterile (PGMS) lines, 2 indica wild abortive (WA) lines, 1 indica BT lines, 4 conventional indica cultivars, and 2 japonica cultivars), all F_1 s had green leaves, indicating that the purple leaf character of OPL and PL 184

was recessive. This trait can therefore be used as a gene marker in hybrid rice breeding.

We investigated leaf color at the seedling stage (about five leaves) in the F_2 generation of 14 crosses between PL 184 or OPL and green lines (Table 1). Crosses 1 and 2 had a 3:1 genetic ratio for green:purple, indicating that PL 184 and W9056S or W8013S differed in one pair of genes. Crosses 3-8 had a 13:3 genetic ratio for green:purple, indicating differences between parents were based on two pairs of genes, one of which was an inhibitory gene. Crosses 9-13 had a 55:9 genetic ratio, indicating that differences between green and purple parents were based on three pairs of genes, one of which was an inhibitory gene. The F_2 s from HN5S/PL 184 had a 229:27 genetic ratio, indicating that differences between parents were based on four gene pairs, one of which was an inhibitory gene.

Although the green:purple ratios in the F_2 s of Zhen-shan 97 A/PL 184 and HN5S/PL 184 differed, both backcrosses had a genetic ratio of 1:1 (Table 2), which confirmed an inhibitory gene in the gene system of the purple character in rice. Furthermore, the ratio of green:purple in triple cross Shuang-guang S//W9056S/PL 184 was 113:15, indicating that inhibitory genes in W9056S and Shuang-guang S were nonallelic.

Purple-leafed sterile plants were found in all F_2 s of crosses with TGMS or PGMS lines, indicating that purple genes and TGMS or PGMS can be combined into one line. Several purple-leafed TGMS lines have been developed. However, crossing these lines with normal green rice varieties produced F_1 s with green leaves, and PL 184-5 and IR1552 had better maintainer ability than Zhen-shan 97 A. The results suggest possibility of using purple leaf character as a gene marker in hybrid rice breeding.

Table 1. Segregation and genetic ratio of seedling leaf color in F_2 populations from crosses between purple and green rice varieties.

Cross	Total plants (no.)	Green plants (no.)	Purple plants (no.)	Genetic ratio	χ^2	P
W9056 S/PL 184	1,081	827	254	3:1	1.2239	0.50-0.25
W8013 S/PL 184	1,361	1,038	323	3:1	1.0994	0.50-0.25
Shuang-guang S/PL 184	5,360	4,352	1,008	13:3	0.0077	0.90-0.75
Zhen-shan 97 A/PL 184	12,034	9,833	2,201	13:3	1.6425	0.25-0.10
Mi-ai 64 S/PL 184	17,898	14,520	3,378	13:3	0.1711	0.75-0.50
Pei-Ai 64 S/PL 184	6,025	4,852	1,175	13:3	1.9957	0.25-0.10
Yue-tai A/PL 184	2,034	1,655	379	13:3	0.0116	0.90-0.75
W91273 S/PL 184	2,699	2,173	526	13:3	0.9153	0.50-0.25
W6068 S/PL 184	8,127	6,947	1,180	55:9	1.3669	0.25-0.10
An-nong S/OPL	4,809	4,158	651	55:9	1.0557	0.50-0.25
3285 S/PL 184	4,720	4,030	690	55:9	1.1624	0.50-0.25
W91238 S/PL 184	3,969	3,439	530	55:9	1.5882	0.25-0.10
E47 S/PL 184	1,671	1,448	223	55:9	0.6549	0.50-0.25
HN5 S/PL 184	4,143	3,698	445	229:27	0.1454	0.75-0.50

Table 2. Segregation and genetic ratio of seedling leaf color in testcross F_1 and three way cross F_1 .

Cross	Generation	Total plants (no.)	Green plants (no.)	Purple plants (no.)	Genetic ratio	χ^2	P
Zhen-shan 97 A/PL 184// PL 184	TC	148	76	72	1:1	0.0608	0.90-0.75
HN5 S/PL 184//PL 184	TC	110	62	48	1:1	1.5364	0.25-0.10
Shuang-guang S//W9056 S/ PL 184	F_2	8434	7400	1034	113:15	2.3311	0.25-0.10

Cited references

- Kinoshita T. 1984. Gene analysis and linkage map. In: S. Tsund, N Takashi. editors. Biology or rice. Tokyo: JSSP/Elsevier. p 187-274.
- Nagao S. 1951. Gene analysis and linkage relationship of characters in rice. Adv. Genet. 4:181-212. ■